

Deliverable

Project Acronym:	VRTogether
Grant Agreement number:	762111
Project Title:	<i>An end-to-end system for the production and delivery of photorealistic social immersive virtual reality experiences</i>

D5.9 - Documentation and technical fact sheets v3

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Dissemination Level		
P	Public	x
C	Confidential, only for members of the consortium and the Commission Services	

Abstract: This deliverable is a compilation of all printed material produced so far, used for dissemination and communication purposes. In addition to the items compiled in D5.7 and D5.8, this deliverable includes new printed materials produced in the third year (actually 15 months period time following the accepted extension **from M25 to M39, October 2019 to December 2020**): 6 posters, 3 commercial fact sheets, 10 technical fact sheet. These materials were used in the different commercial and scientific events, such as IBC, VRDays Europe, ICT, IEEE VR, ACM MMSys, ACM IMX and ACM CHI.

REVISION HISTORY

Revision	Date	Author	Organisation	Description
0.1	14/12/2020	Mària Sanchez	i2CAT	First release
0.2	11/01/2021	Iván Rodríguez	i2CAT	Second release – All sections updated
0.3	12/01/2021	Pascal Perrot	Viaccess-Orca	Review
1.0	14/01/2021	Sergi Fernández	i2CAT	Submission to the EC

Disclaimer

The information, documentation and figures available in this deliverable, is written by the **VRTogether** (An end-to-end system for the production and delivery of photorealistic social immersive virtual reality experiences) – project consortium under EC grant agreement -ICT-2016-762111 and does not necessarily reflect the views of the European Commission. The European Commission is not liable for any use that may be made of the information contained herein.

Statement of originality:

This document contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation or both.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document is a compilation of printed dissemination material (including technical information). In this third and final release, the materials provided in D5.7 and D5.8 are supplemented by updates to these documents, as well as newly created ones.

This wide range of printed communication materials have been produced to present the project and its outcomes. Contents have been specifically created to meet the needs of each channel/audience, always with a clear and appealing approach.

These materials have been used in the global events where VRTogether has been showcased throughout the project's lifetime, including industry and scientific events such as IBC, VRDays Europe, ICT, IEEE VR, ACM MMSys, ACM IMX and ACM CHI, among others. However, in 2020, many of these events shifted to a virtual format in response to the COVID-19. Consequently, these printed materials have been adapted to be used as digital assets to support the project's participation in virtual events.

Since the beginning of the project, a wide range of fact sheets and brochures with different approaches (technical, general info, commercial, etc.) have been designed and produced, in order to give detailed explanations of the developments achieved at various dissemination events. Initial versions were focused on general information about the project (i.e.: scope, objectives, and technologies to be developed) and technical insights of the pilots, while subsequent versions were later developed to present the achievements of the project and its current status. In narrow coordination with the exploitation team, a final set of fact sheets detailing the main features of VRTogether's key technology components were produced in order to communicate technical details to stakeholders in an accessible way.

Furthermore, larger printed displays, such as posters and roll-up banners, were produced to disseminate the project in scientific events, and as a marketing tool for trade shows and exhibitions, both physical and virtual.

The material is accessible and downloadable through the project website: <http://vrtogether.eu/project-outcomes/dissemination-materials/>

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1. INTRODUCTION

This deliverable is a compilation of all printed material produced so far, used for dissemination and communication purposes. In addition to the items compiled in D5.7 and D5.8, this deliverable includes new printed materials produced in the third year (actually, a 15 months period time following the accepted extension, means **from M25 to M39, October 2019 to December 2020**).

The document is mainly structured in two parts. The first part lists all the documents produced throughout the project's lifetime. The list provides also a brief description of the document. The second part of the document provides the documents.

2. PROJECT DOCUMENTATION

2.1. List of material

Name	Version	Description	Release date	Author
Logo	1.0	A logo that was initially used in internal documents and later would be improved.	2017 October 17	Entropy
Logo	2.0	Different formats of multi colored and dynamic logo	2017 November 12	Entropy
Project image	1.0	A stock image to have a recurrent resource to be used in the several dissemination materials that transmits the project concept.	2017 November 29	i2CAT
Project image	2.0	A stock image emphasizing the social side of the project.	2017 November 29	i2CAT
Poster	1.0	A poster that introduces the project and its objectives. This poster was used in order to present the project ImmersiaTV during the workshop "Collaboration Towards the Future of Media" (organised by the EU) in Brussels on October 10th, 2017. It shows the project objectives and milestones	2017 October 10	i2CAT
Poster	2.0	An A1 poster featuring a description of the first pilot, an overview of the configuration modes and a diagram showing the platform architecture. It has been displayed at VRTogether's lab nodes, as well as in events such as CERTH-ITI Open Day 2019 and NEM 2019.	2019 January 21	i2CAT
Poster Social VR	3.0	An A1 poster presenting a general overview of the project, focused on the pipelines, platform characteristics and products. It was displayed at VRTogether's booth at IBC 2019.	2019 July 19	i2CAT
Poster Products	3.0	An A1 poster detailing the actual exploitation opportunities, including 2 end-to-end products, 2 main components and 1 evaluation service. It was displayed at VRTogether's booth at IBC 2019.	2019 July 19	i2CAT
Poster Technological Innovations	3.0	An A1 poster detailing the platform architecture and the specific innovations in terms of technology	2019 July 19	i2CAT
Poster Pilots	3.0	An A1 poster detailing the roadmap and each of the pilots, as well as the evaluation methodology.	2019 July 19	i2CAT
Commercial Fact sheet	1.0	An item that introduces the project and has been frequently used in the more initial phase of period 1: IBC 2017, NEM Summit 2017, MMSYS2018 and TVX 2018	2017 November 29	i2CAT
Commercial Fact sheet	2.0	A flyer with a more commercial bias that can be used in order to reach and engage the industrial stakeholders	2018 September 13	Entropy, i2CAT

Commercial Fact sheet	3.0	A slight update of v2.0. This accordion-fold brochure presents the project and its objectives, provides an updated overview of the pilots and lists VRTogether's potential products and main features. It was distributed at IBC 2019.	2019 September 6	Entropy, i2CAT	
Technical fact sheet	1.0	Design of a general document that explains the main technical aspects of the first Pilot and the demo shown. It has been used during IBC2018.	2018 September 13	Entropy	
Technical Fact sheet Web pipeline	2.0	An A4, double-sided fact sheet showing the key features of the end-to-end web-based framework. It was distributed at IBC 2019.	2019 July 24	TNO, i2CAT	
Technical Fact sheet Volumetric video	2.0	An A4, double-sided fact sheet showing the key features of the volumetric video production system. It was distributed at IBC 2019.	2019 September 6	CERTH, i2CAT	
Technical Fact sheet Scalable ultra-low latency Point-Clouds and TVM transmission SDK	2.0	An A4, double-sided fact sheet showing the key features of the PC and TVM transmission SDK.	2019 October	Motion Spell, i2CAT	
Technical Fact sheet Scalable ultra-low latency Point-Clouds and TVM transmission SDK	3.0	A set of A4, double-sided fact sheets of the VRTogether's key components, presenting their main features and providing a snapshot of the platform and the interrelations among its components.	2020 October	Motion Spell, i2CAT	
Technical Fact sheet Point Cloud Encoding and Decoding	3.0		2020 November	CWI, i2CAT	
Technical Fact sheet Web-based social VR platform	3.0		2020 November	TNO, i2CAT	
Technical Fact sheet Point cloud objective quality metrics	3.0		2020 November	CWI, i2CAT	
Technical Fact sheet VolumetricCapturing System	3.0		2020 November	CERTH, i2CAT	
Technical Fact sheet Media/Session Orchestrator	3.0		2020 November	Viaccess- Orca, Motion Spell, i2CAT	
Roll up	1.0		A roll up designed to grasp visitors' attention during the IBC2018 and inviting them to test the demo. It contains a market-oriented claim, the members of the consortium and the EU flag.	2018 October 29	i2CAT

3. LOGO

3.1. v1.0

3.2. v2.0

4. PROJECT IMAGE

4.1. v1.0

4.2. v2.0

5. POSTER

5.1. v1.0

In this project, our aim is to radically improve the experience by innovating in how media formats are used (i.e., how audio, video and graphics are captured, delivered and rendered at users' homes) demonstrating a significant improvement of **the feeling of being there together** and the **photorealistic quality of the content**.

OBJECTIVES

A
Develop and integrate new media formats that deliver high quality photo-realistic content and create a strong feeling of co-presence in coherently integrated experiences.

B
Adapt the existing production pipeline to capture and encode multiple media formats and integrate them with state-of-the-art post-production tools.

C
Re-Design the distribution chain so such innovative content format can be orchestrated and delivered in a scalable manner.

D
Develop appropriate Quality of Experience (QoE) metrics and evaluation methods to quantify the quality of these new social VR experiences.

E
Maximize the impact of VR-Together can have on content creators, producers, distributors, tooling companies, service providers and the general audience.

MILESTONES

3 pilots addressing 3 different production format in a unified architecture.

Intimate Concert
Offline pilot to demonstrate that the Innovative media format of VR-Together (orchestrating point clouds, 3DMesh based models and multiple video sources) can produce a more intimate and binding activity.

Live news
Live production of multi-source Immersive content that takes the user to the location where news are occurring while sharing them with other people.

Interactive Fiction
Pilot to demonstrate how the VR-Together platform, in a custom-designed content production process, can allow for a novel form of content where users meet, and blend within the interactive immersive experience

GRANT NUMBER 762111
DURATION 3 years (2017-2020)
BUDGET 3.9M€

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This project has been funded by the European Commission as part of the H2020 program, under the grant agreement 762111

Project Coordinator & Technical Lead

VRTogether's consortium has been strategically set up to consist of partners that cover all stages of the production chain in a well-balanced way. A combination of leading academic institutions **I2CAT, TNO, CWI, CERTH, Artanim** together with industry actors **Future Lighthouse, Entropy, Motion Spell, Viaccess-Orca** spread over 5 European countries.

5.2. v2.0

VRTogether

AN END-TO-END SYSTEM FOR THE PRODUCTION AND DELIVERY OF
PHOTOREALISTIC SOCIAL IMMERSIVE VIRTUAL REALITY EXPERIENCES

**SOCIAL VR LIKE
NEVER SEEN BEFORE**

PILOT 1: POLICE INTERROGATION
Two users watch a police interrogation from the dark side of the room. After the interrogatory, the users can interact and discuss about the scene.

WEB BASED CONFIGURATION
A WebRTC powered full body reconstruction employing RGB + depth information.

TIME VARYING MESH CONFIGURATION
A 3D full body reconstruction employing meshes and using RabbitMQ for its transmission.

POINT CLOUD CONFIGURATION
A 3D full body reconstruction employing point clouds and working over DASH.

The diagram illustrates the end-to-end system architecture. It starts with two users (User 01 and User 02) who capture their environment. The captured data (video and audio) is processed through an 'Encoding & Encapsulation' stage, which involves encoding, encapsulation, and packaging. The data is then delivered via a network to a 'Web Server' and a 'Hand Set'. On the client side, the data is received and processed through a 'Playback' stage, which includes video playback, audio playback, and user interaction. The final output is a 'Decodification' stage, which involves decoding, de-encapsulation, and de-packing. The system is supported by various components like a 'Camera', 'Microphone', 'Speaker', and 'Display'.

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This project has been funded by the European Commission under the Horizon 2020 programme. Project No. 101019711

5.3. v3.0

5.3.1. Social VR

AN END-TO-END SYSTEM FOR THE PRODUCTION AND DELIVERY OF

PHOTOREALISTIC SOCIAL IMMERSIVE VIRTUAL REALITY EXPERIENCES

SOCIAL VR LIKE NEVER SEEN BEFORE

VRTogether aims at enabling social Virtual Reality experiences that allow a natural interaction between **remote users immersed in a shared virtual environment** in an affordable way and with photo-realistic quality. It also explores the hybridization of content formats—2D, 3D, Point Clouds and Time Varying Meshes (TVM)—to achieve **the highest quality of experience possible** while keeping production costs under reasonable limits.

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VRTogether PIPELINES

VRTogether PLATFORM CHARACTERISTICS

- Multimedia delivery chain Workflow development 3D rendering engines
- Encoding & encapsulation of content stream Live motion capture
- 3D characters reconstruction with TVMs or Point Clouds
- Data orchestration within the information flow

PRODUCTS

Lightweight social VR service

Volumetric data end to end transmission system

4D Capture System

Point Cloud MCU

New protocol and metrics to evaluate social VR

5.3.2. Products

AN END-TO-END SYSTEM FOR THE PRODUCTION AND DELIVERY OF

PHOTOREALISTIC SOCIAL IMMERSIVE VIRTUAL REALITY EXPERIENCES

VRTogether

Lightweight social VR service

E2E Solution

Real-time E2E communication system. Based on web technologies (HTML5, Javascript, WebRTC and WebGL APIs), combined with video coding and distribution standards like DASH, it provides an efficient VR based conferencing system.

Volumetric data end to end transmission system

Component

It allows any kind of volumetric data (Point Clouds or mesh) to be transmitted to a final system by including smart layers of filtering and compression.

4D Capture System

Component

It enables multi-RGBD, Point Cloud and TVM real time acquisition. The 4D Capture system will provide the opportunity to capture users even for XR applications since it will offer an automatic, smart HMD removal option.

Point Cloud - MCU

E2E Solution

A key and strategical part of a real time E2E communication system, which can be considered as holographic conferencing system.

New protocol and metrics to evaluate social VR

Service

A set of objective metrics that can monitor (and predict) QoE, in a software package; and a set of guidelines and protocol for others to follow, developed to meet the evaluation needs of a new medium such as social VR.

PRODUCTS

The VRTogether project is developing **2 end-to-end products** that offer a complete solution to experiment social Virtual Reality; **2 main components** that can be proposed as standalone components; and **1 evaluation service** for new protocols and metrics for social VR (sVR) evaluation.

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5.3.3. Technological Innovations

AN END-TO-END SYSTEM FOR THE PRODUCTION AND DELIVERY OF

PHOTOREALISTIC SOCIAL IMMERSIVE VIRTUAL REALITY EXPERIENCES

TECHNOLOGICAL INNOVATIONS

VRTogether is innovating in terms of various user representation media in social-VR, enabling immersion and interaction between **multiple remote users** within VR environments. Depth-sensors technology enable volumetric capturing thanks to RGB-D view acquisition. From a single RGB-D view processing to a rig of multiple RGB-D views, thanks to **mesh-based** and **point cloud-based** reconstruction algorithms, the production of low-latency volumetric video streams is now a true envision.

Aiming to provide technologies for highly responsive and realistic user interaction, VRTogether is innovating on **media encoding, transmission and rendering** in an efficient and orchestrated way.

To enhance immersion, VRTogether is researching on sophisticated **HMD removal** methods, targeting more natural interaction between VR users.

	LOCATION	PROCESS	DoF	STREAM
WEB	 Home Based VR	 RGB+Depth	 3DoF+	 WebRTC
	 Location Based VR	 TVM Point Clouds	 6DoF	 DASH

→ STREAMS (TVM, PC, 2D)
→ LIVE STREAMS (2D BILLBOARD)
→ STREAMS (ON DEMAND CONTENT)
→ WEBSOCKETS (socket.io)
- - - COMMANDS

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5.3.4. Pilots

AN END-TO-END SYSTEM FOR THE PRODUCTION AND DELIVERY OF

PHOTOREALISTIC SOCIAL IMMERSIVE VIRTUAL REALITY EXPERIENCES

PILOTS

VRTogether is assembling an end-to-end workflow for Social Virtual Reality content production. Development updates are presented through three pilots, three episodes of **a great story about a murder investigation**. The storyline exploits the uniqueness of the project, a team composed of technical and artistic experts, by creating a new experience that makes the most of the writing possibilities.

A coherent storyline across 3 pilots

1 Feeling of being there (presence) and of being there together (togetherness)

Two users watch a police interrogation of a murder suspect from the dark side of the room. During the experience, the users can interact and talk about the scene while seeing each other in a photo-realistic quality 3D representation.

2 REMOTE COLLABORATION

Live media and scalability

Four users are placed in a TV news studio where the presenter is giving an overview of the news of the day. When the murder is being reported, users are holo-ported to the crime scene where a journalist relates the details of the murder.

The final pilot will conclude the presented story, with users being able to interact with objects and characters in the scene, driving the scenario through their interactions.

3 INTERACTION AND 6DOF

Users are able to interact remotely in a shared VR world

All their actions are delivered in real time

A 3D reconstruction of the users body is provided

You can see the other users interacting as themselves

EVALUATION METHODOLOGY

Objective Metrics

- Performance Metrics
- Users' behavior (gestures, head movements)

Subjective Metrics

- Questionnaires
- Semi-structured interviews

DEPLOYMENT

- Collaborative User Lab Inter-connected nodes in Greece, The Netherlands & Spain
- Scientific & Industrial events

WATCH PILOT 1

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6. COMMERCIAL FACT SHEET

6.1. v1.0

In this project, our aim is to radically improve the experience by innovating in how media formats are used (i.e., how audio, video and graphics are captured, delivered and rendered at users' homes) demonstrating a significant improvement of the feeling of being there together and the photorealistic quality of the content.

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Partners: ICGAT, TNO, CWI, GRIIT, ARJANIM, Future Lighthouse, Entropy, Motion Spell, MESHify

This project has been funded by the European Commission as part of the H2020 program, under the grant agreement 101017117

VRTogether

Coordinating partner: @VRTogether_EU

VRTogether's consortium has been strategically set up to consist of partners that cover all stages of the production chain in a well-balanced way.

A combination of leading academic institutions (ICGAT, TNO, CWI, GRIIT), Arjanim together with industry actors Future Lighthouse, Entropy, Motion Spell, Vaccam-Cica spread over 5 European countries.

MAIN OBJECTIVES

- Develop and integrate user needs to create high quality photo-realistic content and create a strong feeling of presence in user-generated experiences.
- Design the architecture of the system to ensure content creation can be accelerated and delivered in a timely manner.
- Maximize the impact of VRTogether on user experience creation, production, distribution, hosting, consumption, service provision and the general audience.
- Adapt the existing production pipeline to capture and create multiple media formats and integrate them with state-of-the-art production tools.
- Develop appropriate quality of Experience (QoE) metrics and evaluation methods to quantify the quality of these new social VR experiences.

MILESTONES

- Deliverable Content**
Offering prior to development the most innovative media format of VR Together through existing pipelines, efficient-based models and multiple video-streams to produce a more realistic and fluid activity.
- User access**
The generalization of user access to VR content that takes into account the location where users access while sharing with other people.
- Interoperability of Content**
Offering to demonstrate how the VR Together platform in a content-driven content production process, can allow for a new level of content where users create, and share within the interactive virtual experience.

6.2. v2.0

PILOTS

Three pilots, three different episodes of a great story about a murder investigation.

Pilot 1: Police interrogation

Two users watch a police interrogation from the dark side of the room. During the experience, the users can interact and talk about the scene while seeing each other in a photo-realistic quality 3D representation.

Pilot 2: Live scenario

Several users experience a live scenario: they are taken to a news broadcast set where, following the story, the background changes and they can view and examine the crime scene.

Pilot 3: Interactivity

Extending the experience of the other pilots, users interact with the virtual environment with cause-effect actions.

APPLICATIONS & USE CASES

Current Social Virtual Reality applications focus on abstract user representations, with simplified avatar representations.

VR-Together now offers the possibility of meeting friends, family and colleagues with a photo-realistic look-alike representation, which brings better support to a multitude of emerging applications, such as business meetings and educational experiences.

GOOD FOR

- Business meetings
- Family experiences
- Educational purposes
- Social networks
- Entertainment
- Games

MAIN FEATURES

The main characteristics of the VR-Together platform are:

- Multimedia delivery chain workflow development
- Live motion capture
- 3D rendering engines
- Encoding and encapsulation of content stream
- 3D characters reconstruction with Time Varying Meshes or Point Clouds
- Data orchestration within the information flow

EXPECTED IMPACT

To set a new standard in social VR using off-the-shelf products

OBJECTIVES

1. Develop and integrate new media formats that deliver high quality photo-realistic content and create a strong feeling of co-experience in coherently integrated experience.
2. Adapt the existing production pipeline to capture and encode multiple media formats and integrate them with state-of-the-art post-production tools.
3. Re-Design the distribution chain so such innovative content format can be orchestrated and delivered in a scalable manner.
4. Develop appropriate Quality of Experience (QoE) metrics and evaluation methods to quantify the quality of these new social VR experiences.
5. Maximize the impact of VR-Together can have on content creators, producers, distributors, tooling companies, service providers and the general audience.

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PARTNERS

This project has been funded by the European Commission as part of the H2020 program, under the grant agreement 742111

PHOTO-REALISTIC IMMERSIVE CONTENT

VR-Together project aims to offer ground-breaking social Virtual Reality (VR) experiences between users located in remote domestic scenarios, based on photo-realistic immersive content, in a cost-effective manner.

VR-Together's consortium has been strategically set up to consist of partners that cover all stages of the production chain in a well-balanced way.

A combination of leading research institutions i2CAT, TNO, CWI, CERTH, Artanim together with industry actors Entropy, Motion Spell, Viaccess-Orca spread over 4 European countries.

6.3. v3.0

OBJECTIVES

- 1 Develop and integrate new media formats that deliver high quality photo-realistic content and create a strong feeling of co-presence in coherently integrated experience.
- 2 Adapt the existing production pipeline to capture and encode multiple media formats and integrate them with state-of-the-art post-production tools.
- 3 Re-design the distribution chain so such innovative content format can be orchestrated and delivered in a scalable manner.
- 4 Develop appropriate Quality of Experience (QoE) metrics and evaluation methods to quantify the quality of these new social VR experiences.
- 5 Maximize the impact that VRTogether can have on content creators, producers, distributors, tooling companies, service providers and the general audience.

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SOCIAL VR LIKE NEVER SEEN BEFORE

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PILOTS

Development updates are presented through three pilots, three episodes of a great story about a murder investigation.

Pilot 1: Feeling of being there (presence) and of being there together (togetherness)

Two users watch a police interrogation of a murder suspect from the dark side of the room. During the experience, the users can interact and talk about the scene while seeing each other in a photo-realistic quality 3D representation.

Pilot 2: Live media and scalability

Four users are placed in a TV news studio where the presenter is giving an overview of the news of the day. When the murder is being reported, users are holo-ported to the crime scene where a journalist relates the details of the murder.

Pilot 3: Interaction and 6DoF

The final pilot will conclude the presented story, with users being able to interact with objects and characters in the scene, driving the scenario through their interactions.

APPLICATIONS & USE CASES

Current Social Virtual Reality applications focus on abstract user representations, with simplified avatar representations.

VRTogether now offers the possibility of meeting friends, family and colleagues with a photo-realistic look-alike representation, which brings better support to a multitude of emerging applications, such as business meetings and educational experiences.

PRODUCTS

MAIN FEATURES

- Multimedia delivery chain
- 3D rendering engines
- Workflow development
- Live motion capture
- Encoding & encapsulation of content stream
- 3D characters reconstruction with TVMs or Point Clouds
- Data orchestration within the information flow

EXPECTED IMPACT

To set a new standard in social VR using off-the-shelf products

7. TECHNICAL FACT SHEET

7.1. v1.0

WEB BASED CONFIGURATION

Capture and delivery

This is a basic web-based configuration employed in VR-Together. For the capturing process, the Kinect V2 or the RealSense D415 camera is used. For the streaming process, the WebRTC framework is used.

The foreground/background segmentation is based on the depth image. A reference image (RGB + depth) is captured before a user is present in the scene. Next, each frame of the captured video is processed. The depth image of each frame is compared to the reference frame to determine the foreground, i.e. the image of the user. This depth map is cleaned up, and applied to the RGB image to retrieve the user's RGB foreground image. The sequence of images, retrieved in this way, is offered as a virtual webcam to the WebRTC framework.

The delivery is currently based on the SimpleWebRTC framework. The Media Capture API is used to retrieve both the virtual webcam and the HMD's microphone. Sessions are set up between the various users under supervision of the Orchestration component. The media is exchanged in a peer-to-peer fashion between the clients involved in the session.

Additional developments in this configuration involve:

Applying the captured RGB-D into a Point Cloud that is overlaid on the captured users position, to show a self view;

Streaming the captured depth images to other clients to allow a 3D image reconstruction at the receiving side;

Play-out

For rendering, the A-Frame framework is used, which is based on WebVR. In this framework, various objects can be combined into a single VR experience. In the basic scenario, a 360 degree photo is used as a virtual environment. In this environment, 2D planes are placed at the other users' positions, and their video (containing only their foreground) is displayed on these 2D planes. The accompanying audio, which is synchronized with the video by using the WebRTC framework, is also placed at the users' positions.

Object-based audio is supported through the integration of the Google Resonance framework. For display of 3D objects, i.e. self-representation of a user or representation of other users, custom shaders that support the employed RGB + depth format for display in a 3D fashion have been developed while the 3D room model object is supported by A-Frame by default.

The project has been funded by the European Commission as part of the Horizon 2020 program under the grant agreement 101017111.

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https://www.simplewebrtc.com/
https://aframe.io/
https://developers.google.com/webvr/spec/1.1/

PLATFORM ARCHITECTURE

COMPONENTS DESCRIPTION

The software architecture of the end-to-end VR-Together (i.e. from capture to consumption chain) is comprised of 5 main components. These components serve as a basis of the integrated platform structure, and each one of them is a conceptual entity related to a general task within the end-to-end communication system.

The Capturing component captures / produces the visual and audio data, performs content reconstruction tasks and synchronizes the captures audio and video signals.

The Encoding & Encapsulation component encodes, encapsulates and packages the audio and video signals received from the previous component into a single stream.

The Delivery component makes this content available for consumption on the network.

The Orchestration component provides end-users with the information necessary to initiate a communication session over the VR-Together platform.

The Play-Out component is responsible for rendering and presentation of the immersive contents. It includes the controls for the shared virtual scenario and end-users' representation. It includes modules for unpacking, demuxing and decoding and synchronizing the audio-visual content.

TIME VARYING MESH CONFIGURATION

Capture and delivery

A full-body 3D user representation is reconstructed (real-time) in a 3D mesh form, i.e. a set of connected vertices and polygons applying UV texturing. The capturing of color and depth information is realized by multiple calibrated RGB-D cameras including the processing of spatial mapping and alignment of the captured 2.5D data into 3D, resulting in a watertight 3D TMM which is reconstructed in real-time. TMMs contain multiple RGB textures, one per RGB-D device, as well as the 3D geometrical information of the mesh, i.e. the vertices, polygons and the corresponding normal vectors.

Due to the data intensive nature of TMMs, compression for fast and efficient transmission via web-based scenarios is necessary. TMMs are compressed both on the level of textures as well as in that of the 3D mesh. 3D data is compressed employing state-of-the-art methods (e.g. Draco, Cortol) while for the textures the TurboJPEG library is used. Subsequently, the compressed data are serialized (packaged) and distributed by a RabbitMQ server, allowing for the VR-Together player to connect and retrieve the transferred information in real-time.

Play-out

Following the information retrieval at the player's side, the packaged TMMs are deserialized and decoded prior to the final step, namely the TMM rendering. To this end, the transferred RGB textures are blended to colorize the 3D mesh within a Unity 3D scene. In particular, the textures are weighted based on the confidence given by the angle difference between the normal of the corresponding polygons and the camera view axis, thus, higher angles correspond to lower confidence.

The audio is mixed locally to reflect the position of every audio object, and is affected by the position and rotation of each user and element in the virtual environment.

Such a practice provides a photo-realistic 3D environment where 3D assets, stereoscopic billboards and 2D user representations are seamlessly presented in a synchronized manner.

Each user starts a session where he or she can socially interact with the other person, being each one of them able to experience a different part of the story via their Head Mounted Displays (HMDs).

https://github.com/jogipal/wco
https://github.com/toni-ruiz/realtime
https://i2cat.com/

POINT CLOUD CONFIGURATION

Capture and delivery

A volumetric representation of the user is captured in real-time as a Point Cloud, i.e. a set of independent points in space, each associated to its spatial coordinates and an RGB triplet indicating the color of the point. The capture is performed by a signal acquisition module, developed by CWI, that merges the data captured by multiple texture + depth Intel RealSense sensors, positioned around the user. The capture module outputs a raw Point Cloud frame and the corresponding capture timestamp at a variable frame rate.

The raw Point Cloud would require extremely high bandwidth to be transmitted over bandwidth-limited networks. Therefore, in order to enable delivery of the Point Cloud signal, each Point Cloud frame is delivered as input to a lossy encoder, developed by CWI, which reduces the bitrate needed to represent the volumetric signal, by removing visual redundancy. The output of the encoding module is an encoded Point Cloud frame. The capture timestamp is also included in the encoded stream to enable their synchronized presentation.

Finally each encoded Point Cloud frame is packed into a DASH segment (i.e., m4s file), by an application based on the Signalis framework, developed by Motion Spell. The m4s files corresponding to temporally consecutive Point Cloud frames are stored on a DASH server, ready to be delivered via HTTP.

Play-out

The incoming packaged Point Cloud frames are handed at the receiver side by using GStreamer framework. An HTTP connection is established to first obtain the MPD and then request the DASH segments composing the stream. From the DASH segments, the Point Cloud structure is extracted and sent to the Point Cloud decoder. The inserted timestamps at the capture side are extracted and used by a developed synchronization module to allow the presentation of all incoming data in a synchronized manner.

A native Point Cloud renderer module was developed to enable user representation in that format. It is based on the wrapper for Unity of Intel RealSense SDK 2.0, which transforms the raw data from the RGB Camera and the Depth Sensor into a Unity 3D mesh.

https://github.com/jogipal/wco
https://github.com/toni-ruiz/realtime
https://i2cat.com/

7.2. v2.0

7.2.1. Web pipeline

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 761974.

END-TO-END WEB-BASED FRAMEWORK TO BUILD AND CONSUME SHARED AND SOCIAL VR EXPERIENCES

FEATURES

Simplified Technology Pipeline

- Use of Web-based components:
 - » WebRTC for communication.
 - » WebVR, WebGL for rendering.
 - » React, Node.js and A-Frame for UI frontend.
- Using common off-the-shelf and consumer grade equipment for capture and display.

Fully orchestrated

- Session management, with per session setup options.
- Multi-person capture and rendering management.
- Synchronisation of live and virtual content.

REAL-TIME LIVE CAPTURE

- Live 3D capture of users using RGB-D cameras (e.g. Kinect or Realsense).
- Provide self-view and HMD removal for local user.

PEER-TO-PEER OR BRIDGED COMMUNICATION

- Communication service through WebRTC.
- Peer-to-peer or if needed for scalability through a VR bridge, combining all individual participant's streams in one large stream.

EASY INTEGRATION OF VIRTUAL ENVIRONMENT

- Support for photo-realistic 360 video and virtual 3D environments.
- Multiple concurrent sources possible, eg. live streaming video in a virtual environment.

SIMPLIFIED TECHNOLOGY PIPELINE

WEB ARCHITECTURE OVERVIEW

VRTogether

AN END-TO-END SYSTEM FOR THE
PRODUCTION AND DELIVERY OF
**PHOTOREALISTIC SOCIAL IMMERSIVE
VIRTUAL REALITY EXPERIENCES**

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7.2.2. Volumetric video

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 761974.

END-TO-END VOLUMETRIC VIDEO PRODUCTION SYSTEM FOR IMMERSIVE VR EXPERIENCES

TECHNOLOGY FEATURES

Portable

- Flexible and light-weight sensor calibration.

Low-cost

- Low-specification hardware resources for multi-RGBD data acquisition.
- Off-the-shelf RGBD sensors (i.e. Intel RealSense D400 series, Azure Kinect DK).

Scalable

- Support of variant number of sensors to alter the associated equipment cost and complexity, depending on the level of geometry detail and visual quality.

VOLUMETRIC VIDEO PRODUCTION

- Real-time (online) volumetric media streaming.
- Support of live self-view representation to boost immersion.
- Content creation through volumetric media recording and post-processing.

REAL-TIME VOLUMETRIC VIDEO COMPRESSION

- State-of-the-art geometry libraries integration.
- Multi-view texture compression.

EASY INTEGRATION OF VIRTUAL ENVIRONMENT

- Game engine plug & play compatibility (e.g. Unity3D, Unreal Engine 4).
- Support of photo-realistic 360° and 3D environments.
- 6 Degrees of Freedom for the user.

SIMPLIFIED TECHNOLOGY PIPELINE

NATIVE ARCHITECTURE OVERVIEW

VRTogether

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7.2.3. Volumetric video

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END-TO-END WEB-BASED FRAMEWORK TO BUILD AND CONSUME SHARED AND SOCIAL VR EXPERIENCES

FEATURES

Simplified Technology Pipeline

- Use of Web-based components:
 - » WebRTC for communication.
 - » WebVR, WebGL for rendering.
 - » React, Node.js and A-Frame for UI frontend.
- Using common off-the-shelf and consumer grade equipment for capture and display.

Fully orchestrated

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- Multi-person capture and rendering management.
- Synchronisation of live and virtual content.

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- Live 3D capture of users using RGB-D cameras (e.g. Kinect or Realsense).
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PEER-TO-PEER OR BRIDGED COMMUNICATION

- Communication service through WebRTC.
- Peer-to-peer or if needed for scalability through a VR bridge, combining all individual participant's streams in one large stream.

EASY INTEGRATION OF VIRTUAL ENVIRONMENT

- Support for photo-realistic 360 video and virtual 3D environments.
- Multiple concurrent sources possible, eg. live streaming video in a virtual environment.

SIMPLIFIED TECHNOLOGY PIPELINE

WEB ARCHITECTURE OVERVIEW

AN END-TO-END SYSTEM FOR THE PRODUCTION AND DELIVERY OF PHOTOREALISTIC SOCIAL IMMERSIVE VIRTUAL REALITY EXPERIENCES

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7.3. V3.0

7.3.1. Scalable ultra-low latency Point-Clouds and TVM transmission SDK

VRTogether

Capture Encode Network Decode & Deliver User Interface

Scalable ultra-low latency Point-Clouds and TVM transmission SDK

developed by MOTION SPELL

This SDK transports volumetric data from end to end using existing scalable networks such as CDNs. Potential applications include AR/VR/XR with real-time interactions (Social VR, Gaming, healthcare, manufacturing, education/training, live events, military and defence, real estate and virtual shopping, ...) and movie production involving the compression, storage and live preview of volumetric data.

SDK Key features

1. Provides an end-to-end transmission SDK for all platforms. Includes a streaming component (native only), some optional server components (native only), and a reception component (native, Web and mobile).
2. Enables ultra-low latency transmission (this latency is the addition of 1 frame processing, the network transmission time and the player buffering).
3. Low footprint in term of CPU, memory and network overhead.
4. Delivers 3D volumetric content as well as video, audio, subtitles and metadata.
5. Includes an SFU (Stream Forwarding Unit) allowing to relay streams with zero-latency. Ideal for testing or for events that don't involve a CDN.
6. Keeps compatibility with existing CDNs and with edge-computing to scale the number of viewers while keeping latency low.
7. Integrates an optional MCU (Media Composition Unit) to handle server-side adaptive bitrate (ABR) with up to 80% gains. May be CPU intensive.

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Scalable ultra-low latency Point-Clouds and TVM transmission SDK

A turnkey solution

Volumetric video and 3+/6DoF contents are still innovative formats. Our team can accommodate and help you with:

- A comprehensive offer including capture, encode, transmission, and playback (native, mobile, and Web) software and expertise.
- Providing and licensing software according to your needs.
- A service offer including trainings, customer developments, and support.

Technical description

- MPEG-DASH over CMAF.
- Adapts to any kind of volumetric data from Point Clouds (V-PCC, G-PCC), Mesh/TVM, MPEG 3+/6DoF, or using a generic container to transport your own data your own way.
- Enables to handle legacy media: video, audio, subtitles, metadata (including timed metadata).
- Can operate in three modes: live, linear or on-demand.
- Offers a smart layer system enhancing adaptive filtering, compression and buffering optimization that can leverage existing player optimizations.
- Uses the latest works from standardization organization such as MPEG, DVB, ATSC.

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About VRTogether

VRTogether is an end-to-end system for the production and delivery of **photorealistic and Social Virtual Reality (Social VR)** experiences.

VRTogether enables Social VR experiences that allow a **natural interaction between remote users** immersed in a shared virtual environment in an affordable way and with photorealistic quality. The project's key exploitable components cover the whole Social VR pipeline:

- Volumetric Capturing System
- Simple Point Cloud Capture System
- Point Cloud Encoding & Decoding
- Scalable Ultra-Low Latency Volumetric Data Transmission
- Media/Session Orchestrator
- Live Presenter (MS)
- Point Cloud - Multipoint Control Unit
- Objective Metrics
- Unity Player
- Web-based Social VR Platform

Consortium

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7.3.2. Point Cloud Encoding and Decoding

Capture

Encode

Network

Decode
& Deliver

User
Interface

Point Cloud Encoding and Decoding

developed by

This component offers a generic real-time dynamic point cloud codec for 3D immersive video. Low delay encoding and decoding at multiple levels of detail make the codec suitable for real time mixed reality applications where point cloud reconstructions are acquired at a high frame rate. A flexible implementation allows integration with any other component in the pipeline

Key Features

1. A generic compression framework that supports point clouds with arbitrary topology regardless of capture system
2. An efficient lossy color attribute coder that takes advantage of collocated points to encode color data using existing image coding standards
3. A real time implementation that allows low delay encode and decode on commodity hardware benefitting from multi-core architectures and a parallel implementation
4. Allows optimization of the experience by using the adaptation capabilities offered by the codec
5. A turnkey solution compatible with multiple delivery systems such as DASH, Multipoint Control Units and point to point AMQP

Point Cloud Encoding and Decoding

Realtime point cloud compression

Point clouds have emerged as a popular representation for real time volumetric reconstructions. This component offers low delay encode and decode suitable for real time applications.

- Scalable to point clouds of arbitrary size and topology
- Open source component (<https://github.com/cwi-dis/cwi-pcl-codec>) used by standards bodies as an anchor codec to develop future codecs

Schematic of Point Cloud Codec

Technical Description

- Octree based geometry compression supporting multiple levels of detail
- JPEG based low delay attribute compression for colors leveraging naturalistic source of color for co-located points
- Hybrid architecture that combines octree occupancy point coding with hybrid schemes common in video coding

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7.3.3. Web-based social VR platform

Web-based social VR platform

developed by **TNO** innovation for life

A fully end-to-end lightweight platform for capture, distribution and consumption of social VR, based on web standards and common components.

Simplified Technology Pipeline

- Use of Web-based components:
 - WebRTC, WebXR, WebGL for communication
 - AngularJS, Node.js and A-Frame for UI frontend
- Built based on video pipeline on top of dash.js, the reference player for Moving Picture Experts Group (MPEG) Dynamic Adaptive Streaming over HTTP (DASH).
- Using common of the shelf and consumer grade equipment for capture and display

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Web-based social VR platform

Fully orchestrated

- Session management, with per session setup options
- Multi-person capture and rendering management
- Synchronisation of live and virtual environments

Real-time live capture

- 1 consumer grade RGB-plus-depth camera per participant (eg. Intel RealSense, MS Kinect4Azure)
- Foreground and background removal keeping only the image of the participant

Peer-to-peer or bridged communication

- Communication service through WebRTC
- Peer-to-peer or client-server topology through a VR bridge, combining all individual participant's streams in 1 stream

Easy integration of virtual environment

- Support for 360 video capture of real environment and virtual, constructed environments
- Multiple concurrent sources possible, eg. live streaming video in a virtual environment

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7.3.4. Point cloud objective quality metrics

Capture

Encode

Network

Decode & Deliver

User Interface

Point cloud objective quality metrics

developed by

Objective quality metrics are used to automatically predict the visual quality of a content, without asking users. They are widely used by video streaming operators to measure the quality of service. New metrics for volumetric video, like ours, are sought after, as they can be used to drive compression optimization engines, or to optimize distortions applied at the receiver side, or at MCU level.

Key features

1. First metric for volumetric video that can be used at the transmitter or receiver side
2. Lightweight features which can be computed in real time
3. No reference needed: suitable for video conferencing and streaming
4. Accurate and reliable
5. Turnkey solution that can be plugged in any existing system for volumetric video delivery

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Point cloud objective quality metrics

Objective quality metrics are used to predict the quality of experience of media objects. They can be divided in three categories:

- Full reference: if the original, undistorted content is available
- Reduced reference: if some information from the original content is available
- No reference: if no information from the original content is available

Our objective quality metrics include:

- A full reference metric for volumetric video that can be used to optimize compression engines at the transmitter side
- First-ever reduced and no reference metrics for volumetric video, that can predict the visual quality at the receiver side

Technical description

- Independent component, implemented in Python, that measures the visual quality of volumetric video contents
- Cloud-based solution that can operate in real time
- Flexible interface for integration in an existing system

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7.3.5. VolumetricCapturing System

Capture

Encode

Network

Decode & Deliver

User Interface

Volumetric Capturing System

developed by CERTH
CENTRE FOR RESEARCH & TECHNOLOGY HELLAS

Volumetric Capturing system of CERTH enables the creation of immersive and compelling virtual reality content by creating advanced virtual humans. Aim of the volumetric capturing system is to be integrated with VR, AR, MR & VFX technologies and game engines (i.e. Unity3D) and equip professional creative studios, with a flexible and portable solution for fast production.

Key features

The Volumetric capture system enables real-like social experiences as fine details of the representations add more reality features to the experience, like facial expressions, which capture the emotional state of each user.

- **Portability:** The system is modular, flexible and has a light-weight sensor calibration system
- **Low-cost:** The use of consumer-grade sensors (i.e RealSense, Azure Kinect) combined with low specification hardware resources for multi-RGBD data acquisition and system openness creates an affordable HW&SW set up
- **Scalable:** Support of variant number of sensors to adjust the associated equipment cost and complexity depending on the level of geometry detail and visual quality.

Realistic content creation

Real time capturing

Easy to use

The Volumetric Video Production offers Real-time (online) volumetric media streaming and can support live self-view representation that increases immersion. With reduced technical background needed, users have more time to focus on the creative part of the capturing

Volumetric Capturing System

Real-time Volumetric Video Compression

Volumetric capturing system offers state-of-the-art geometry libraries integration and multi-view texture compression. The technology pipeline is simple and straightforward.

Capture > Process > Compress > Stream > Render

System openness

The publicly available software of volumetric capturing facilitates the proof-of-concept content creation in a budget friendly way. Users avoid expensive production of 3D media using 3D modeling software.

Easy Integration of Virtual Environment

The proposed multi view capturing and calibration system enables the generation of high quality realistic 3D assets meeting creators needs. It allows 4D data export in several data formats allowing for easy use in any widely used software tool. It offers:

- Game engine plug & play compatibility (e.g. Unity 3D, Unreal Engine 4)
- Support of photo-realistic 360 and 3D environments
- 6 Degrees of freedom for the user

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7.3.6. Media/Session Orchestrator

Capture

Encode

Network

Decode & Deliver

User Interface

Media/Session Orchestrator

developed by MOTION SPELL

The Orchestration framework brings to the Social VR Platform all the logics and intelligence to manage and connect multiple users in complex virtual environments. It simplifies the integration of live-photorealistic user representations into complex scenarios allowing to share virtual experience together.

Key features

1. Automated configuration, coordination, and management of user sessions.
2. Schedules and controls the full execution of the platform components and communication layers between users.
3. Real-time communication over connected node
4. Management of virtual room services for SocialVR, Teleconferencing, MeetingRoom

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Media/Session Orchestrator

The Orchestrator component is the heart of the complete VRTogether solution that schedules and controls the full execution of components and communication between users. The schema below shows the central role of the orchestrator component:

VRT orchestrator functionalities:

- 1. Authentication and logging:** Validating credentials sent by the users and log them on the orchestrator.
- 2. Session management:** Handling users into sessions and rooms according to scenarios and manage the execution of a scenario.
- 3. Messages communication:** handle messages communication between users.
- 4. Pilot and monitor delivery components:** instantiate media distribution component according to session and monitoring the streams management.
- 5. Common time provider:** for helping synchronization of media on user side.
- 6. Logs and Analytics framework:** the orchestrator provides full logging and analytic services to help developers to tune their user components.
- 7. Media transmission backup layer:** orchestration includes some specific functions to provide backup generic streams transmission functions.

Technical description

- JavaScript API relying on the Node.js open-source platform
- C# client-side API
- Based JSON schemas to define the structure of client requests and server response

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8. ROLL-UP

8.1. v1.0

The poster features a woman wearing a VR headset, smiling. The background is a gradient from purple to orange. The text is white and purple.

VRTogether
PHOTO-REALISTIC IMMERSIVE CONTENT

SOCIAL VR DEMO

Available to try now!

i2cat **CERTH** **CWI** **TNO** **ENTROPY** **viaccess-orca** **MOTION SPELL** **ertanim** **European Commission**

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